

Mapping of Malaria in Colonial Bengal using GIS

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Abstract: The term 'malaria' was synonymous to any types of fever, which were associated with the terms like Kala-duk, Kala-Azar, Assam-epidemic malarial fever, Burdwan Fever during British rule in Colonial Bengal. There are multiple available research works on (deaths due to) malaria in Colonial Bengal. Geographic Information System (GIS) mapping in historical studies, especially in malaria, is very limited. In this present study, GIS mapping of malaria is a very novel task. The QGIS 3.16 Hannover has been used in the present study to map the spatial distribution of malaria in Colonial Bengal. The QGIS maps help us to explore the exact locations of the death events due to malaria. From 1836 to the independence of India (1947), Bengal experienced the heaviest death toll due to malaria, though the first malaria death was recorded in Calcutta (Presently Kolkata) in 1690 and it caused 460 deaths. All the death locations were mapped in GIS environment that would also help to identify the major geographical and other factors of malaria.

Keywords: Malaria, Colonial Bengal, Burdwan Fever, Kala-Azar, Kala-duk, GIS Maps.

1. Introduction

The word 'Colonial Bengal' represents the British-occupied Bengal Province after the decisive victory at the battle of Plassey in 1757 by the East India Company. The entire Bengal Presidency can be divided into two provinces viz. Upper Provinces and the Lower Provinces. In 1836, separate administration was also formed for those two Provinces. The Upper Provinces were named North-Western Provinces (Hunter, 1908), and the Lower Provinces were known as Bengal Province. The Lower Provinces were comprised of four sub-provinces i.e., Bengal Proper, Bihar, Chota Nagpur, and Orissa Province, and some Native States i.e., Cooch Behar, Sikkim, Hill Tippera and twenty-six Tributary States of Orissa and Chota Nagpur (Campbell, 2003). The present study deals with the Bengal Proper sub-province under the Lower Bengal Provinces (Figure 1). Geopolitically and historically, the Bengal Proper is situated in the south-eastern part of Asia and in the eastern part of India, at the apex of Bay of Bengal. It (excluding Cooch Behar and Hill Tippera) covered a geographical area of approximately 1038 million sq km. (Bentley, 1925a). According to O'Malley (1913), the Bengal province comprised five administrative divisions under four natural parts, namely (i) the Western Bengal: comprised of all the districts under Burdwan Division, i.e., Burdwan, Birbhum, Bankura, Midnapur, Hooghly and Howrah; (ii) the Eastern Bengal: composed of all the districts under Presidency Division, i.e., 24 parganas, Calcutta, Murshidabad, Nadia, Jessore and Khulna; (iii) the Northern Bengal: comprised of all the districts under Rajsahi division, i.e., Bogra, Rajsahi, Pabna, Malda, Rangpur, Dinajpur, Jalpaiguri and Darjeeling; and (iv) the Central Bengal: composed of all the districts under Dacca and Chittagong division, i.e., the Dacca Division, which is comprised of Dacca, Mymensingh, Backarganj, Faridpur, and the Chittagong Division comprised of Noakhali, Tippera, Hill Tippera, Chittagong, and Chittagong hill tracts (Samanta, 2002).

Looking at the prevalence of various diseases, it could be claimed by the authors that Bengal was the laboratory of various diseases and many of them appeared in their epidemic forms. Among all the epidemics malaria, cholera, plague, diarrhoea, dysentery, smallpox, influenza, tuberculosis,

leprosy etc. were common (O'Malley, 1913), and among which malaria (identically), plague, cholera and smallpox were the most destructive (Palit, 2008). Only Bengal experienced approximately 40% of malaria cases and deaths out of the total disease cases and deaths occurred in the whole of India (Ray, 1998). Thus, the present study, mapping malaria in Colonial Bengal from 1836 to 1947 has been framed for understanding the extent of malaria in Colonial Bengal using Geographic Information System (GIS). The geographical and other associated factors of the malaria epidemic within the study area also will be explored through the GIS environment for getting a detailed scenario of these historical events, which is a novel idea for the subject (History).

2. Literature Review

There are several research publications on (deaths due to) malaria in Colonial Bengal. (Bentley, 1916; Bird, 1866; Klein, 1972; Samanta, 2002; Ray, 1998). Few of the available literature did not use the term 'Malaria' directly, but it could be understood that any death due to 'fever' was synonymous with 'malaria' (Lyons, 1871; Mitter, 1876). On the other hand, the 'Kala-Azar' or 'Kala-duk' (Malley, 1907), 'Assam epidemic malarial fever' (Chatterjee, 1923; Gupta, 1944; Rogers, 1897), and 'Burdwan Fever' (Lyons, 1872; Brahmachari, 1911) were also synonymously used with malaria fever in some other literatures. This is to mention that from this section onwards, malaria would be used instead of all the above-mentioned types of fevers. The previous researchers have identified various aspects like rainfall, temperature, elevation, forest cover (Hu et al., 1998); unrefined drinking water supply by municipalities (Rogers, 1900); marshy lands, agricultural lands, and siltation of rivers (Klein, 1972; Bentley, 1925a; Samanta, 2002); dampness for obstructed drainage by roads, railways (Mitter, 1876; Klein, 1972); and wet rice and jute cultivation adjacent to the homesteads (Samanta, 2002) as responsible factors for the spreading as well as intensification of this disease. Most of the above-mentioned studies includes basically the description and chronological records of the number of deaths due to malaria, their major locations, and the

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fatal effects of fever along with a few factors of malaria. Almost all of the above-mentioned research publications have investigated and analysed the archival data from the West Bengal State Archive, Government documents like reports of Sanitary Commissioner of Bengal, District Gazetteers, and Census Reports etc. But very few researchers have used maps for understanding the spatial distribution of the malarial zones in their research articles (Dutta and Dutt, 1978; Sarkar, 1931; Bentley, 1925a) and those maps are basically very obscure from Geographers' perspective because of creating difficulty of visualising any location. As the locational extents of any phenomena on the Earth's surface can easily be represented through mapping techniques, it is the simplest method to show geographical distribution of any event or phenomena. Mapping with the latest techniques (GIS tools) also helps to visualise the fact. Very few studies have used the GIS technology for temporal analysis of diseases in the past. Kuo and Fukui have shown the spatio-temporal study of disease diffusion patterns of cholera between 1882 and 1895 in Fukushima Prefecture in Japan using GIS and geo-statistical techniques (Kuo and Fukui, 2007). Koulentaki with his other co-researchers have studied the spatio-temporal analysis i.e., prevalence and incidence and mapping of spatial distribution of the patients of primary biliary cirrhosis disease in Crete Island of Greece in between 1980 and 2010 (Koulentaki et al., 2014). Although malaria disease has been mapped in the GIS environment by very few researchers worldwide (Qayum et al., 2015; Dogan et al., 2010), the present article is the first one on the analysis of malaria diseases in Colonial Bengal using the GIS technology. So, this research work must add a new dimension with the existing studies in the study of malaria in Colonial Bengal using GIS.

3. Objective

The main objective of the present study is to map the extent of malaria in Colonial Bengal using GIS, which would also help to explore the geographical and other associated factors of the malaria epidemic within the study area.

4. Methods and Materials

Bringing old maps and data into the GIS domain was the prime target of this paper to achieve the objective of the present study. The administrative divisions of the Bengal Proper were extracted in the GIS environment from the Government report i.e., Census of India, 1921, Vol. V, Bengal, Part I Report by W. H. Thompson (1923), as the administrative boundaries of the study area was the same as in 1836. The FOSS4G (Free and Open Source Software for Geospatial), *QGIS 3.16 Hannover* was used for the visualisation of various aspects of malaria.

Malaria events and resultant death records were collected from different historical sources. These are listed as follows:

i. Bengal District Gazetteers of the Districts of Bengal (WBSA, 1869; WBSA, 1863; Malley, 1907; O'malley, 1908a; O'malley, 1908b; O'malley, 1908c; O'Malley, 1909; Garrett, 1910; Gupta, 1910; O'Malley, 1910; Peterson, 1910; Gruning, 1911; Malley, 1911; Vas, 1911; Webster, 1911; Allen, 1912; O'Malley, 1912a; O'Malley, 1912b; Strong, 1912; O'Malley, 1914a; O'Malley, 1914b; O'Malley, 1916; Sachse, 1917; Jack, 1918; Lambourn, 1918; O'Malley, 1923; Bentley, 1925a; Banerji, 1972).

ii. West Bengal State Archive (WBSA).

iii. Imperial Gazette of India (Hunter, 1908; Frowde, 1909).

iv. Government reports (O'Malley, 1913; Thompson, 1923; Bentley, 1925a).

v. Books (Ray, 1998; Samanta, 2002).

The detailed spatial analyses of malaria outbreaks with the associated deaths were done on the basis of above stated data sources indicating the place names. The Google Map was used for finding the absolute locations of those places within the study area. Further, the extracted data were tabulated and arranged by using Microsoft Excel. Finally, the datasets were utilised in the GIS environment (*QGIS 3.16 Hannover*) for mapping (Figure 2).

5. Limitations

• Methods of investigation of the epidemic

The death statistics of people, which were recorded by the village *Chaukidars* from 1869, were practically full of inconsistencies. Many of those reports were also incomplete, inaccurate and unreliable because the village *Chaukidars* were not well trained for collecting the data and they hardly had the medical knowledge about diseases or to distinguish the diseases from one another. So, they were not able to differentiate the febrile symptoms of malaria from the rest of the diseases e.g. bronchitis, pneumonia, phthisis, typhoid, Leishman-Donovan infection etc. An experiment shows that out of 2616 deaths recorded in the thanas (Police Stations), 1056 were reported wrongly (O'Malley, 1913; Peterson, 1910). After introducing the new procedure for recording vital statistics, the *Chaukidars* were ordered to report the birth and death statistics to the police on parade days in 1892 and the police were requested to submit the monthly report to the civil surgeons, who were engaged to complete the report of that entire district.

• Difficulty to plot the historical places

In some cases, the older names of the places have got altered into other names at present. So, it is difficult to find the exact geolocations of those historical places on the maps and to plot in the GIS environment.

5. Results and Findings

In Bengal province, malaria was known to people even since the Vedic period (Samanta, 2002), but the actual records of malaria and the deaths associated with it were not recorded until the beginning of the 20th century. From an account of 1911 (Table 1), it is clear from the GIS maps (Figure 3) that the Western (94.48 %) and Central (89.99 %) portions of colonial Bengal were major malaria or fever infected areas, whereas the people of Eastern Bengal was experienced only 28.68 % (Bentley, 1925a).

The death due to malaria was recorded nearly 460 for the first time in Calcutta, presently known as Kolkata (Samanta, 2002) in 1690 (Figure 3). After a long pause, Marquis of Wellesley indicated the unhealthiness and prevalence of malarial fever in 1770 among the troops at Berhampur of Murshidabad district (Ray, 1998). According to Dr. Thomas (Lambourn, 1918), fever due to malaria was prevalent at Goa Malti, Englishbazar Thana, and Shibganj Thana at the end of the eighteenth century (Figure 3), but it became annual phenomenon in later periods throughout Bengal with millions of deaths.

Bengal experienced a spate of malaria during the early nineteenth and twentieth Century. In 1832, the Ula or Beeranagar village in Nadia District faced a scourge of malaria fever though no death was recorded at this event (Ray, 1998). Again in 1836, Mohammadpur Village of Jessore District in Bengal Province (**Figure 3**) exceeded the earliest record of malaria epidemic in terms of ferocity (O'Malley, 1912b; O'Malley, 1913; Ray, 1998; Bentley, 1925a). The disease affected almost 700 convicts of Sitaram Rai's Jail and 150 died among the affected people. As suggested by Dr Elliot, the region was experiencing malaria fever since 1824 (O'Malley, 1912b). The epidemic continued in the region till 1843. After that, it took a little pause for about three years and again appeared in 1846 with more intensity than before affecting the whole district till 1848. After the event of 1848, it again took a pause of six to eight years and came back again in 1854-56. After that, it started to spread westward i.e., Nadia and 24 Parganas. The deaths were recorded as approximately 10,000 in the second phase due to the malaria epidemic in the Ula village of Nadia district (**Figure 3**) from 1856-62 (WBSA, 1863). The fever gradually continued its westward movement from Presidency Division to Burdwan Division and affected the region, particularly during 1869-1874 by taking the name 'Burdwan Fever' (O'Malley, 1912b). In 1862, the dreadful epidemic fever attacked Burdwan District for the first time, while the district was very much salutiferous before that time because of providing better treatment facilities to the common people for curing various diseases. After Nadia District, the fever crossed the river Bhagirathi and spread to the riverside villages of Cutwa (Katwa), Parbasthali (Purbasthali) and Culna (Kalna) Thana in 1862 and 1863. Afterwards, it spread in Hooghly and Howrah Districts from 1864 to 1867 and spread far to the north and south, the epidemic invaded Burdwan Town in 1868-69. From 1870 to 1872, the whole Birbhum District with surrounding large portions, i.e., the north-eastern part of Midnapur District was affected. In 1873, no further perversion happened and slight abatement of the disease was started in the Burdwan Division, in spite of having more severity in Howrah and Midnapur District than the previous year. The disease started to die out prominently after 1874, which was also considered the last year of that epidemic course (Rogers, 1897). According to the estimation of Dr. French, nearly one-third of the total mortality of the districts was only due to epidemic fever. Almost 13,313 died among the 46,000 population (about 30 per cent of the district's total population) in that fever only throughout Burdwan Town from 1869 to 1872. The Census report of 1881 shows that approximately 750,000 people died from the epidemic in the District from 1862-74 (Peterson, 1910).

Some locations related to the major epidemic events from 1861-70 were found to be clustered in Central and Western Bengal. Among them, the notorious places for the number of deaths were Pandua of Hooghly District with 5,222 deaths, followed by Ichapur Village under Ganguriah Thana of Burdwan District with 5,200 deaths in 1862. Other deaths (**Figure 4**) due to fever were occurred in Calcutta, Bansberia, Meherpur, Makurgram, Meghshar etc. (Samanta, 2002). The detailed records can also be found in **Appendix 1**.

Bengal Province was composed of five administrative divisions, viz., Rajsahi, Burdwan, Presidency, Dacca and Chittagong. The entire Bengal province was severely

affected by the fever (malaria) epidemic. In both 1885 and 1886, the highest mortality was in Rajsahi division i.e., 171,664 and 199,649 respectively and the lowest mortality was in Chittagong division i.e., 47,231 and 44,991 respectively (Lidderdale, 1887). Malaria mortality was also very high in the other divisions of Bengal province. The Burdwan division experienced 109,360 and 102,188 deaths in 1885 and 1886 respectively, whereas the Dacca division experienced 104,335 and 119,170. In case of the Presidency division, the number of deaths was 156,288 and 135,800 during 1885 and 1886 respectively (**Figure 5**).

From 1911-1920, approximately 10 million people died only in fever over the Bengal Proper, though at that time influenza along with malaria was a common epidemic category under fever class. No other different accounts for malaria, influenza and other febrile diseases are available in the literature. A detailed account of death due to fever from 1911-1920 is given in **Table 2**.

In the 20th Century (up to 1947), the whole province experienced the outbreak of the epidemic fever with the more or less same intensity. Malaria caused the deaths of millions of human lives. Each year from 1921 to 1944 experienced a huge number of deaths (**Table 3**). In 1921, about 0.7 million people died only due to malaria, but the intensity was somewhat low from 1922-42, whereas the number of death increased again to 688,404 and 763,220 in 1943 and 1944 respectively (**Figure 6**) in the whole Bengal Province (Ray, 1998).

6. Discussion and Conclusion

The various pockets of every district in the Bengal province experienced malaria outbreaks, which were shown in the GIS environment for better visualisation and understanding of the severity of that disease. The map (**Figure 7**) shows that the entire Eastern Bengal was least affected than compare to other regional divisions of Bengal. Bentley (1925) pointed out agricultural prosperity as the reason for the healthiness or low incidence of malaria in Eastern Bengal. Chatterjee's (1949) map of the arable land (**Figure 8**) also helps to establish the stated fact. The arable land in terms of the total area is high to very high in the case of Eastern, Central, and Northern Bengal (except the mountainous parts), but it shares moderate to high land holding in the Western Bengal. That is the reason behind the concentration of malarial fever in the western and central parts of Colonial Bengal. Detailed death of some selected districts due to malaria from 1872 to 1911 has also been highlighted in **Figure 9**. **Appendix 2** also helps to get the detailed death statistics during that time frame. Moreover, the meteorological setup (especially rainfall and temperature) is one of the reasons behind the outbreak of malaria in Western and Central Bengal. The regions experienced more than 25.55 °C mean annual temperature (**Figure 10a**) and less than 1524 mm mean annual rainfall (**Figure 10b**) from 1925 to 1944. That is the suitable subtropical climatic condition for the growth of the Anopheles mosquito, which causes malaria. Furthermore, it can be noticed that the concentration of malaria is very less within the zone of salinity (**Figure 11**), but the outbreaks can be seen mainly within the one feet tidal contour. Besides, there has a strong relationship between construction work and the malaria outbreak (**Table 4**) in Colonial Bengal. More specifically, malaria has spread out along the railway tract (**Figure 12**). For that reason, the high concentration can be found in the

Bengal and Presidency Divisions of Bengal Province (Table 5).

Although the frequency and intensity was not same, but almost every district had experienced the scourge of malaria. So, the present article helps to visualise the spatio-temporal distribution of malaria deaths over Colonial Bengal in the GIS environment.

7. Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Department of Geography, The University of Burdwan for pursuing research activities. TR is also thankful to DST PURSE Phase-2 Programme for Research Fellowship (Ref No, R.T.I./PURSE/Phase 2/34).

8. Conflict of interest:

The authors have no conflict of interest.

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Figures with captions:

Figure 1: Showing the study area, Bengal Proper with all its administrative divisions in red boundaries (After Thompson, 1923).

Figure 2: Detailed methodology of representing historical malaria data in the GIS environment (Source: Authors' own creation).

Figure 3: Malaria infected population in percentage over the four divisions of Colonial Bengal with few important locations. The first ever recorded deaths (almost 460) due to malaria in Calcutta is shown by green dot. Yellow dots represent the prevalence of malaria in the Late Eighteenth Century over Bengal. The earliest known record (1836) of malaria epidemic, Muhammadpur has been shown by red dot. Additionally, the second recorded deaths (10,000) in Ula due to the malaria epidemic from 1856-62 has been show by blue dot (Source: Produced by authors).

Figure 4: The locations of some major malaria epidemic events from 1861-1870 (Source: Map is produced by authors).

Figure 5: Death records over the five administrative divisions of Bengal in 1885 and 1886 (Source: Map is produced by authors).

Figure 6: Yearly death records due to malarial fever over the entire Bengal Province from 1921-1947, where the year 1946 and 1947 represent the records of West Bengal only (Source: Diagram is produced by authors).

Figure 7: Showing malarious places throughout the entire Bengal Province (Source: Map is produced by authors).

Figure 8: Arable land over the various part of colonial Bengal (Source: Modified after Chatterjee, 1949).

Figure 9: Malaria death records in some specific districts of Colonial Bengal from 1872-1911 (Source: Map produced by authors).

Figure 10: Mean annual temperature (°C) and mean annual rainfall (mm) distribution over the entire Bengal Province from 1925 to 1944 (Source: Modified after Chatterjee, 1949).

Figure 11: Zone of salinity, one feet tidal contour, and the distribution of marsh land over the deltic part of Colonial Bengal with malarious places (Source: Modified after Chatterjee, 1949).

Figure 12: Expansion of railway tracks (narrow gauge and broad gauge) over the colonial Bengal (Source: Modified after Chatterjee, 1949).

Tables with captions:

Table 1: Malaria or fever infected population of Bengal in 1911 (After Bentley, 1925a).

Regions of Bengal	Total Population (1911)	Fever Infected Population	Percentage (%)
Western Bengal	8,467,314	8,000,000	94.48
Central Bengal	9,445,321	8,500,000	89.99
Northern Bengal	10,138,302	8,500,000	83.84
Eastern Bengal	17,432,140	5,000,000	28.68

Table 2: Deaths due to fever in Bengal Proper from 1911-1920 (After Thompson, 1921).

Year	Total number of deaths
1911	882,276
1912	959,193
1913	965,546
1914	1081,041
1915	1064,159
1916	909,880
1917	882,768
1918	1357,906
1919	1229,257
1920	1144,421

Table 3: Deaths due to Malaria in Bengal Province from 1921-1947 (After Ray, 1998).

Place	Year	No. of Deaths
Entire Bengal (Colonial Bengal) Province	1921	737223
	1922	540463
	1923	539899
	1924	527902
	1925	497473
	1926	458208
	1927	429143
	1928	368691
	1929	335414

1930	336879	
1931	349111	
1932	327386	
1933	413922	
1934	387191	
1935	342955	
1936	337647	
1937	372992	
1938	416521	
1939	341321	
1940	369448	
1941	388381	
1942	426573	
1943	688404	
1944	763220	
1945	516099	
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Bengal (Only West Bengal)	1946	103339
	1947	82539

Table 4: Relationship between major construction projects in Colonial Bengal and malaria outbreak (After Samanta, 2002 and Banerji, 1972).

Year	Major Projects (Railways/ Roadways/ River)	Outbreak of malaria occurred
1824	Jessore - Dacca road construction	Muhammadpur and Jessore districts
1836	Construction of Jessore - Faridpur high road	Jessore district
1855	Inundation caused by destruction of embankments along right bank of River Damodar	Ula of Nadia district
1858	Construction of embankment in Nabaganga River	Magura, Narail, and Jhenidah
1861	Communication through railway between Howrah and Rajmahal in Bihar	Nayasarai, Jirat, Balagarh, Jagaddal, Garulia, Sripur, and Somra
1862	Eastern Bengal Railway on the eastern side of Hooghly river: 45 miles between Calcutta and Ranighat in Nadia district.	Barrackpur, Titagarh, Khardah, and Guptipara
1862	Railway embankment along the eastern border of the villages	Ichapur to Chakdah, Halisahar, and Kanchrapara (severe outbreak)
1862	Construction of two roads in the vicinity of Pandua to Kalna	A scourge of fever from Pandua to Kalna
1868 - 1869	In Jahanabad (presently Arambag), a road constructed, meeting the G.T Road at Mayapur and extended up to Khanakul. Besides, the canals of Jalalalpur, Arakul, Satmasha, and Girgatola etc. flowed into Kana Nadi were closed.	Outbreak in the surrounding villages
1871	Construction of Eden Canal (Damodar River) took as a project in 1871 and opened in 1881	Severe malaria outbreak between 1872 and 1891 in Burdwan district decreased the total population by 94,535
1873	Embankment of a canal in the vicinity of Krishtanagar Police Station and Hooghly	Krishtanagar Police Station and Hooghly
1885	The Dacca State Railway originating from Narayanganj to Mymensingh	Throughout Dacca division with the death of nearly 104,335 people

1896	Assam - Bengal Railway from Gauhati to Lumding	Fever became prevalent in Nowgang
1907	Murshidabad branch of Eastern Bengal Railway	Murshidabad district
1910	Construction of Railway in Malda District	Malda district

Table 5: Railway track length in different Bengal divisions (Source: Authors' own creation).

Divisions	Length (km)	
	Broad Gauge	Narrow Gauge
Burdwan	829.70	-
Presidency	879.71	-
Dacca	256.96	386.77
Rajshahi	412.48	745.44
Chittagong	-	375.06

Appendix:

Appendix 1: Events of malarial deaths in different places of Colonial Bengal (After Samanta, 2002 and Banerji, 1972).

Places	Year	No. of Deaths from malaria
Calcutta	1690	460
Muhammadpur, Jessore	1836	~700
Ula (Nadia)	1856-62	10,000
Bansberia	1861	700
Makurgram	1861	500
Tribeni	1861	645
Burdwan Town	1862-74	750,000
Pandua	1862	5222
Ichapur Village (Ganguriah P.S.)	1862	5200
Barasat	1862	400
Parbatpur	1863	100
Calcutta	1863	1959

Sonatikri	1863	700
Baligari	1863	1284
Balagarh	1863	2271
Parambu	1863	2169
Shahbazar	1863	2176
Somaspur	1863	2737
Dwarbasini	1863	1959
Meherpur	1863	2300
Rajhat	1863	1400
Meghshar	1864	662
Ula	1864	1000
Dwarhatta	1866	3045
Mamudpur	1868	937
Dhaniyakhali	1868	697
Makurgram	1868	937
Pandua	1868	393
Chakpur-Mohanbati	1868	86
Parbatpur	1869	171
Burdwan Town	1869-72	13,313

Appendix 2: Death records of malaria in some districts of Colonial Bengal (After Samanta, 2002 and Bengal District Gazetteers of the selected districts).

Districts	Year	Deaths
Midnapur	1872	25000
Birbhum	1876	35000
Hooghly	1876	65000
Howrah	1881	50000
Rangpur	1902	62471
Nadia	1903	55527
Murshidabad	1903	39596
Khulna	1903	26063
Tippera	1905	40000
Chittagong	1905	36091
Bogra	1905	20826
Darjeeling	1905	12704
Dinajpur	1906	65096
Jalpaiguri	1907	25149
Burdwan	1907	45815
Noakhali	1908	25094
Backerganj	1911	37040
Malda	1911	32434